

Phospho - AKT

3.20.18

30 min.

#1

#2

#3

Phospha

GapdH

3.27.18

#1

#2

#3

Total A27 155

3.20.18

#1 ✓

#2

#3 ✓

Total
Gap 471

3.27.18

#1 ✓

#2 ✓

#3 ✓